

METHODS OF DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCES REQUIRED BY THE STANDARDS OF INTERNATIONAL EVALUATION PROGRAMS IN FUTURE BIOLOGY TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the methods of developing students' mathematical, scientific and reading literacy, as well as creative thinking and problem-solving basic competencies based on the requirements of the International Assessment Program for future biology teachers.*

Keywords : *PISA TIMSS, mathematical literacy, scientific literacy, basic competence, integration, modern methods.*

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PF-134 dated May 11, 2022, adopted in order to develop the quality of education in our country, participate in international evaluation research programs and take a worthy place Decree of approval, Decision No. PQ-289 dated June 21, 2022 "On measures to improve the quality of pedagogical education and further develop the activities of higher educational institutions for the training of pedagogical personnel" in the country 2030 by 2018, it has set a priority to become one of the first 30 advanced countries in the world according to the rating of the PISA international assessment program.

In order to ensure the performance of the assigned tasks, scientific research is being conducted to develop and implement innovative methods of assessment and development of students' reading, mathematical and natural-scientific literacy, creative thinking related to the International Assessment Research PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS programs. .

The main part

The teacher plays an integral role in students' acquisition and understanding of concepts and knowledge in the textbook. Accordingly, he assumes responsibility for understanding scientific content and presenting it in a way that is relevant to student learning, known as pedagogical content knowledge (PMB). It is a "central feature of the knowledge base of teaching" that requires "a depth of understanding of subject knowledge structures." Improving teachers' PMB depends on experience, lesson planning, and classroom instructional practices. The main sources of the teacher's knowledge base include general content knowledge, attitudes, pedagogical knowledge, educational goals and context, as well as learning resources. the level of knowledge develops. [5]

Future biology teachers should develop tasks related to the cognitive field, learn through communication, learn in cooperation according to the mastery of students, apply the principle of "learning by research", apply their knowledge to their lives, to be able to relate to their interests, to organize systematic conversations related to independent education - training, to strengthen the connection between theory and practice, to adapt the content of education to different situations and to be able to apply it The development of skills such as acquiring skills is defined as the priority goals of higher education institutions that train pedagogues. [2]

A number of studies are being conducted in our country regarding this research, including B. Ismailov's research on the topic "Improving the mechanisms for organizing the quality assessment of basic secondary education based on the requirements of the PISA

International Assessment Program" on the cooperative activities of basic schools and schools attached to them. organizational measures are highlighted.

It describes the processes of ensuring the awareness and cooperation of general secondary school leaders and pedagogues in the implementation of assessment mechanisms based on the new approach.

The development of competencies required by the standards of international assessment programs in future biology teachers is being studied as an actual pedagogical problem.

Ball and Hill (2008) classify the knowledge content of pedagogues required of future teachers as follows:

-Content knowledge or subject knowledge: this summarizes the structure of the teacher's teaching material, including the basic concepts of the subject area.

- General pedagogical knowledge: it represents the basic principles that ensure the process of teaching, such as classroom management, teaching skills, learning time, waiting time, based on the principles of individual and group interaction in the classroom.

- knowledge of the curriculum: shows the teacher's knowledge of the curriculum and its main elements, theories, assessment methods, organization of experiments and activities, lesson planning, teaching materials and tools preparing for the exam in addition to using the guides.

- Pedagogical content knowledge: includes content-related knowledge that allows the teacher to teach in real classroom conditions.

- knowledge of students and their characteristics: This means identifying students' interests, learning needs, individual differences, previous experiences and understandings, alternative understandings and appropriate application of knowledge.

- knowledge of educational content: it is related to classroom management, school knowledge, respect for cultural and social diversity among students.

- knowledge of educational goals and values: includes knowledge of the philosophical and historical foundations of education, as well as the professional ethics of teaching.

Natural sciences cycle nature , biology , geography , physics , chemistry study _ subjects enters _ Current in the day integrative study _ for the teaching of Science didactic supply done to increase intended National study program work developed _

Based on the purpose of each subject, the integrative points in the study of natural-scientific phenomena are determined. Also, in the section of subjects, experiment-testing works were carried out in connection with the formation of the following special competencies.

From the subject of mathematics : imagining and understanding mathematical concepts, performing operations on real and complex numbers, applying mathematical knowledge in practice, logical analysis.

From physics : observing, understanding and explaining physical processes and phenomena, measuring and determining physical quantities, conducting experiments and drawing conclusions, being able to use physical knowledge and tools in practice;

From computer science: Competence of collecting information on electronic means, processing information on electronic means, competence of transmitting information through electronic means, application of informatics knowledge in practice;

chemistry : to explain chemical processes and phenomena, to be able to express elements and formulas chemically, to be able to work with necessary equipment for conducting experiments, to apply the knowledge gained from chemistry in practice;

From geography: observing, understanding and explaining natural processes and phenomena, observing economic and social processes, ecological culture, being able to use geographical atlases and maps, applying geographical knowledge in practice;

From the subject of biology: biological process, understanding and explanation of phenomena, environmental culture, working with necessary equipment for conducting experiments, practical application of knowledge gained in biology. In the field of natural and concrete sciences, the system of knowledge that must be acquired by students in order to achieve the above-mentioned goals should be delivered on the basis of psychological, pedagogical and didactic laws, that is, the process of knowing from live observation to abstract thinking and beyond. it should be implemented by putting it into practice. [3]

In fact, a biology teacher must have sufficient knowledge of the above subject system, have resources, understand and understand the tasks required by the International Evaluation Research Program and convey them to the student using effective methods.

M.Ergasheva in the study "Methodology of using assessment programs in monitoring students' natural-scientific literacy" (in the example of PISA, TIMSS) showed that the mutual integration of sciences led to students' understanding of nature as a whole, and the formation of a single natural-scientific view of the world in their thinking. He emphasized that it creates the ground and develops the world of imagination.

At the same time, interdisciplinary integration allows students to combine their knowledge of the opportunities and problems of modern scientific and technical development, the nature of environmental problems, the ways of rational use of nature, the principles of following a healthy lifestyle, and the basics of financial and economic literacy. and it is required to achieve the development of competences to apply in everyday life [4]

Future biology teachers, i.e. graduate students of higher pedagogic education, need modern methods to master international assessment competences and convey them to students.

Ways to implement interdisciplinary communication:

- the sequence and consistency of learning different subjects should be chosen in such a way that learning one of them helps to learn the other;

- achieving a uniform approach to the formation of general understanding, skills, qualifications and competences;

- through the extensive use of knowledge, skills, skills and competencies of other subjects in the study of knowledge, skills, skills and competences of one subject

- educational plans and educational programs are optimized in education;

- independent and logical thinking, abstract and thinking skills are formed in students;

-students are formed comprehensive concepts and ideas about nature, society, science, and life skills. . [10]

In order to achieve the above results, it is necessary to consistently use effective methods in the education process of future teachers.

Unfortunately, knowledge about the content, scope of tasks and fields of science of international evaluation research is not enough in the whole world today. Therefore, there is a great need for research with different approaches.

In fact , it is effective to prepare students for international evaluation studies by using these methods in natural sciences in order to convey the concepts of teaching and learning from biology

to students. It is effective not only in classes, but also for students' independent work tasks outside of class. methods are needed.

In the process of teaching specific subjects, students' scientific worldview is formed through interactive teaching methods, their interest in science is nurtured, and the competences envisaged by them are formed. "Problem", "Brainstorming", "Cluster ("Networks")", "Boomerang", "Decision tree", "Project", "Resume", "Case study" in teaching natural and exact sciences in higher education institutions ", "Fish skeleton", "Venn diagram", "Competitive lesson", "BBB", "FSMU", "Analysis of concepts" and other interactive methods in accordance with the type, goals and tasks and stages of the lessons, students can not only concrete sciences - mathematics, informatics and physical sciences, natural sciences - geography, biology and chemistry, as well as the connection between natural and concrete sciences through practical training, mastering all sciences together, the ability to generalize their knowledge develops in them the ability to apply the knowledge gained from science in life.

Summary

Based on the requirements of international assessment studies, the future biology teachers will be able to use modern teaching methods related to the development of students' mathematical, natural scientific and reading literacy, as well as creative thinking and problem-solving competences. preparation for the use of innovative and integrated methods for formation is an urgent task.

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